

MEDICAL SCIENCES

VITAMIN D AND ITS ROLE ON THE FATIGUE MITIGATION: REVIEW

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Abstract

Vitamin D has historically been associated with bone metabolism. However, over the years, a growing body of evidence has emerged indicating its involvement in various physiological processes that may influence the onset of numerous pathologies (cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases, rheumatological diseases, fertility, cancer, diabetes, or a condition of fatigue). This narrative review investigates the current knowledge of the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying fatigue and the ways in which vitamin D is implicated in these processes. Scientific studies in the databases of PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science were reviewed with a focus on factors that play a role in the genesis of fatigue, where the influence of vitamin D has been clearly demonstrated. The pathogenic factors of fatigue influenced by vitamin D are related to biochemical factors connected to oxidative stress and inflammatory cytokines. A role in the control of the neurotransmitters dopamine and serotonin has also been demonstrated: an imbalance in the relationship between these two neurotransmitters is linked to the genesis of fatigue. Furthermore, vitamin D is implicated in the control of voltage-gated calcium and chloride channels. Although it has been demonstrated that hypovitaminosis D is associated with numerous pathological conditions, current data on the outcomes of correcting hypovitaminosis D are conflicting. This suggests that, despite the significant involvement of vitamin D in regulating mechanisms governing fatigue, other factors could also play a role.

Keywords: vitamin D, oxidative stress, neurotransmitters, chronic fatigue.

The Fatigue

Fatigue is a symptom related to a great variety of physiological and parapsychological conditions, and in many of these, it represents an epiphenomenon. Its manifestations are both peripheral and central, presenting as a condition of weakness and torpor associated with a reduction in muscle strength. This peripheral condition may be due to a pathological condition that affects either the muscle fibers or its control by motor neurons (1). On the contrary, mental fatigue can be associated with a variable degree of cognitive deterioration. In both cases, the result is a negative impact on quality of life. Quantitatively assessing fatigue is challenging due to numerous subjective variables and different classifications. According to work by Engberg et al. (2017), women have higher fatigue scores than men, and among men, higher socioeconomic status and greater physical activity are associated with lower levels of fatigue (2). According to Behrenas et al. (2023), fatigue may be distinguished by the state of fatigue because the latter derives from two factors closely connected to each other: the fatigue objectively attributable to doing something and the fatigue that the patient perceives subjectively (3). Chronic fatigue is an epiphenomenon of both central forms, such as neurological diseases relating to the central, peripheral, and autonomic nervous systems, and peripheral ones, such as

those affecting the neuromuscular junction and metabolic diseases, as well as rheumatologic diseases; furthermore, this symptom also prevails among autoimmune diseases (rheumatological diseases, type 1 diabetes, chronic fatigue syndrome, or celiac disease) (4, 5). Although fatigue is a very disabling symptom that strongly compromises the quality of life, and although its pathophysiology is the subject of numerous studies, the mechanisms that lead to the onset of this symptom are currently not perfectly clear. Many involved features have been identified, including cytokines, some neurotransmitters, factors associated with oxidative stress, and many factors involved in their regulation; among them, there is vitamin D.

Despite substantial evidence for the potential role of vitamin D in regulating fatigue across various pathological conditions, current clinical practices have overlooked the potential impact of vitamin D supplementation on such conditions. We thus conducted this review with two aims in mind: (1) to summarize the knowledge about the effect of vitamin D levels on the occurrence and/or progression of chronic fatigue-related diseases, as determined by *in vitro*, *in vivo* models, and human clinical trials; and (2) to provide a rationale for further investigations (such as randomized clinical trials) to translate current evidence into clinical practice. For this review, we identified scientific studies published up to 2023 in the databases of PubMed, Scopus, and Web of

Science, using search terms that combine “vitamin D”, “vitamin D3”, or “hypovitaminosis D” with the various pathological conditions.

Vitamin D

Vitamin D is a group of lipid-soluble precursors that need to be converted into the active form; the most important compounds in this group are cholecalciferol (D3) and ergocalciferol (D2). D2 differs from D3 because it has a double bond between C22 and C23 and a methyl group at C24 of the side chain. The D3 form is specific to animal species, while the D2 can be found in some vegetable matrices (6). The main sources of vitamin D are two: an endogen and an exogen. The first and most important one consists of the endogenous synthesis at the level of human skin via a UVB light photochemical reaction (7). The second source, which is less decisive, consists of food intake. Food sources include mushrooms and reindeer lichen for D2 and fish, in particular fish liver oils, for D3 (8). Since most mammals are able to synthesize vitamin D3 if adequately exposed to sunlight, the consequence is that it is not considered a vitamin in the strict sense but more as a hormone. Several in-depth revisions of vitamin D sources (both from food and as supplements) can be found in the literature (8).

In a work by Sintzel et al. (2018), the great difference between the self-produced vitamin D and the dietary intake was investigated (9). They calculated that during summer, a 20 min whole body UVB ray exposure session of a Caucasian person may ensure more than 10,000 IU of produced vitamin D3. In contrast, diet provides a very small and less significant contribution, which consists only of 40–400 IU for each average meal.

Both vitamin D2 and D3 need to be activated via two consequential hydroxylation reactions: firstly, at the liver level, where cholecalciferol is converted to calcifediol (25-hydroxycholecalciferol, 25(OH)D) because of a 25-hydroxylase (CYP2R1), and then at the renal level, where calcifediol is further hydroxylated to form calcitriol (1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol, 1,25(OH)₂D) by 1 α -hydroxylase (CYP27B1). Calcitriol is the biologically active form of vitamin D3 in humans (. Furthermore, extra-renal paracrine activation has been demonstrated in >10 extrarenal organs (11).

The main mechanisms that prevent hypervitaminosis resulting from UVB over-exposure are represented both by 24-hydroxylation performed by the enzyme 24-hydroxylase (CYP24A1) and by the degradation of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D produced by the UVB rays themselves (12).

The three main steps, 25-hydroxylation, 1 α -hydroxylation, and 24-hydroxylation, are performed in the endoplasmic reticulum by Cytochrome P450 mixed function oxidases located in CYP2R1, which seems to be the major 25-hydroxylase, or in the mitochondria by CYP27A1, CYP27B1, and CYP24A1 (10). Indeed, the active form of vitamin D is generated not only in renal tubular cells but also in extrarenal target tissue cells, and its functions are autocrine, paracrine, and endocrine.

The vitamin D metabolites are transported in blood bound primarily to vitamin D binding protein

(DBP) (85–88%) and albumin (12–15%) and explicate their function in the target tissues interacting with the Vitamin D Receptor (VDR).

The chemical difference between D2 and D3 results in the different affinity of D2 for DBP (D-binding protein), weaker in D2 than in D3 (13). Both active forms of vitamin D2 and vitamin D3 have comparable affinity for VDR (10).

Vitamin D exerts its biological effects by binding to its intranuclear receptor (VDR); after this binding, a heterodimeric complex with the retinoid X receptor is obtained.

This complex binds VDREs (vitamin D response elements) that are specific sequences distributed in target genes near promoters and involves many coregulatory complexes; all these factors determine the transcriptional output, leading to the expression of numerous specific gene products (14).

The multiplicity and diversity of the effects of vitamin D depend on the different localization of the VDRs, which are present in multiple target organs (15). VDRs have been identified in both the cytoplasm and nucleus, associated with different nuclear membranes. For this reason, the effects of vitamin D can be both genomic and non-genomic (16).

Vitamin D's Impact on the Cytokines: Oxidative Stress and Inflammation

As previously mentioned, oxidative stress and inflammation are major pathways regulating fatigue onset (17).

Many mechanisms are involved in these complex processes, such as redox reactions, ROS (reactive oxygen species) production, and normal mitochondrial functions. Vitamin D was studied as an important regulatory factor that may control these pathways (18).

The activation of vitamin D is enhanced in conditions of cellular stress (19), and the supplementation of vitamin D is able to improve mitochondrial oxidative function in skeletal muscle and reduce oxidative stress in the mitochondria (20). In fact, during oxidative stress conditions, there is an increase in the release of many factors, such as nuclear factor kappa β (NF κ β), inducible NO synthase (iNOS), and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), leading to the enhancement of nitrosative stress and consequently the damage of fatty acids and proteins at the membrane level, all underpinning chronic fatigue (21).

An important vitamin D-regulated mitochondrial pathway consists of the control of Nrf2/PGC-1 α -SIRT3 (22); in this process, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor—coactivator 1 α (PGC-1 α) interacts with Nrf2, generating a complex that modulates SIRT3. Vitamin D ligand–receptor binding increases the transcription of Nrf2, a major regulator of redox signaling, which exerts antioxidant activities by enhancing the expression of numerous genes involved in these pathways (23–26).

Another mechanism of protection from oxidative damage concerns the enhanced expression of the anti-aging protein Klotho (23). Klotho is a gene that encodes for an anti-aging protein with various functions, including increasing the resistance to oxidative stress (27).

Moreover, vitamin D-VDR binding determines a favorable influence on mitochondrial respiration and

inhibits the overproduction of ROS (28). In fact, its chronic deficiency is connected to the formation of ROS and, hence, oxidative damage (18).

Another important role of vitamin D consists of the regulation of the expression of gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (g-GT), which contributes to the synthesis of a reduced form of glutathione (GSH), essential for the activity of glutathione peroxidase (GPX). It is one of the cell's enzymatic antioxidant systems and can increase the activity of other enzymes such as glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD), glutamate-cysteine ligase (CGL), and glutathione reductase, leading to a further increase in GSH (29).

Remarkably, vitamin D can also act at the epigenetic level. Vitamin D can influence the epigenome in multiple ways, such as increasing genomic VDR binding, influencing CCCTC binding factor (CTCF) binding and the formation of topologically associated domains (TADs), affecting the binding of pioneer transcription factor and changing histone modifications and chromatin accessibility (30).

Also, because of its epigenetic effects, vitamin D is a major regulator of the immune system and of inflammatory processes (31). A causal link between vitamin D and inflammation has been demonstrated concerning both the synthesis and release of anti-inflammatory cytokines and direct actions on the cells of the immune system. According to Carlberg et al. (2019), vitamin D modulates the epigenome of immune cells both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, in particular monocytes and their differentiated subtypes (30).

Reducing the differentiation of Th1 lymphocytes, the active form of D, can reduce the secretion of inflammatory cytokines (IL-2, IFN γ , and TNF- α). At the same time, it can promote Th2-type differentiation, increasing the secretion of anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-4, IL-5, and IL-10) (32).

Furthermore, the active form of vitamin D promotes monocyte proliferation and the IL-1 and cathelicidin expression by macrophages and inhibits the proliferation of B cells and their differentiation into plasma cells, consequently reducing immunoglobulins production (3).

Many immune system cells (dendritic cells, monocytes/macrophages, and T and B cells) express 1 α -hydroxylase, so many immune responses can be attributable to VDR (33). In fact, activated T cells can upregulate the VDR, and vitamin D is increased, not only by the expression of VDR but also by cytochrome P450 and CYP27B1 in macrophages and monocytes (3).

In addition, pathogenic T cells produce IL-17, and this is supported by IL-23. The stimulation of this IL-23 cytokine is strongly inhibited by the D-VDR interaction (34). Interestingly, some proinflammatory cytokines (INL-1, INL-6, and INF γ) are often increased in patients with chronic fatigue (35).

Vitamin D's Interaction with Neurotransmitters

It was demonstrated that vitamin D can affect both growth factors and neurotransmitter activity. Concerning the growth factors, for example, a relationship has been demonstrated between vitamin D and NGF (Nerve Growth factor) (36, 37).

Vitamin D3 was reported to increase the levels of NGF, GDNF (glial cell-derived neurotrophic factor), and the expression of p75NTR, a tumor necrosis factor receptor expressed during early neuronal development and in adults, in specific pathological conditions (38). Despite that, no effects on other neurotrophins emerged (39).

Central fatigue relates to the activity of several neurotransmitters, including serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine, angiotensin II, norepinephrine, and nitric oxide; among them, vitamin D seems to influence dopamine and serotonin (40). Vitamin D can carry out its action at the brain level, as VDR has been found in many brain areas (41).

Central fatigue results from an imbalance of dopamine and serotonin within the central nervous system (35, 42, 43). In this scenario, vitamin D has proven to be a key factor in the regulation of neurogenesis and differentiation processes; in fact, according to recent research, a chronic administration of vitamin D can lead to an increase in the ability to release dopamine (44). The authors assessed that vitamin D is a powerful regulator acting on the distribution of synapses, vesicle proteins, and a number of dopaminergic synapses. Moreover, it can improve the function of tyrosine hydroxylase in cells.

Many authors suggest a role for vitamin D as an adjuvant in the treatment of specific pathologies; for instance, vitamin D was studied as an important factor in maintaining the trophism of dopaminergic neurons in Parkinson's disease (45). The same relationship in other morbid conditions, such as attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (46), or in neuropsychiatric diseases was assessed (47). The relationship between vitamin D and fatigue does not only concern its influence on dopamine pathways but also serotonin, as its association with the onset of fatigue was demonstrated. In fact, an alteration of serotonin resulted in an alteration of fatigue (48). This connection was also underlined by Zawadzka et al. (2021), who emphasized how fatigue is linked to an altered central relationship between serotonin and dopamine (49).

The vitamin D-serotonin biochemical relationship derives from vitamin D's influence on the tryptophan hydroxylase transcription, as the hydroxylation of tryptophan is a limiting step in serotonin biosynthesis (50, 51). From a molecular point of view, the ligand-receptor binding would trigger the activation of many genes, including TPH2, which is responsible for vitamin D synthesis and tryptophan metabolism (52).

Moreover, the relationship between the two neurotransmitters, dopamine and serotonin, is of importance as fatigue is related to increased serotonergic activity and decreased dopaminergic activity (40).

Despite this evidence supporting the key role of vitamin D in the modulation of neuronal responses, further data on the correlation between plasma vitamin D and Parkinson's disease or other neuronal disorders should be acquired to support its use within preventive strategies of neurodegeneration.

Vitamin D's Impact on Other Molecular Pathways

Among the other molecular pathways involved in vitamin D activity, it was demonstrated that it can induce the activity of voltage-gated chloride and calcium channels (19). Vitamin D plays a neuroprotective role by modulating L-type voltage-dependent calcium channels via a genomic and a non-genomic mechanism, both via the modulation of substances such as calbindin and by upregulating neurotrophic factors (NGF, GDNF, and NT-3); the modulation of calcium channels performs clear functions on neuronal excitability (53).

With regard to the voltage-dependent chloride channels, according to our current knowledge, the modulation by vitamin D has been demonstrated only at the Sertoli cell level and at the osteoblastic level (54, 55).

Another mechanism of action of vitamin D in reducing fatigue consists of its influence on some characteristics of red blood cells, including the ability to deform when they pass through capillaries; the deformability of red blood cells, which appears to be altered in patients with chronic fatigue, was correlated with plasma levels of 25(OH)D and other substances such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and C-reactive protein (CRP) (56).

Hypovitaminosis D: Causes, Symptoms, and Impact on Fatigue

Vitamin D deficiency occurs when plasma levels of 25(OH)D are below 20 ng/mL (57); levels between 21 and 29 ng/mL define insufficiency, and levels over 30 ng/mL are considered sufficient (58).

A daily dose of 600–800 IU of vitamin D was reported to be enough to guarantee good bone health; however, to have 25(OH)D stable plasma levels higher than 30 ng/mL, an increased intake is necessary (1000–2000 IU) (3).

Many factors influence plasma vitamin D levels, including the time of day, time of year, latitude (in higher latitudes, vitamin D is not produced year-round), skin factors (the presence of clothing and the type and color of the fabric), the use of sunscreen and sun protection factor, the amount of melanin (i.e., African Americans, and dark-skinned populations in general, have lower levels of vitamin D), the presence of damaged skin (scar tissues have a lower capacity to synthesize active vitamin D), the skin temperature (an increase in skin temperature corresponds to a greater speed of skin vitamin synthesis), the number of vitamins ingested and absorbed (many pathologies reduce absorption), and possible obesity (which is associated with lower serum vitamin D concentrations) (59).

Chronic hypovitaminosis D is associated with cardiovascular diseases and metabolic dysfunctions and could be considered an important comorbidity or a risk factor for premature death (60, 61). In fact, inverse relationships have been reported with vitamin D adequacy, with reduced all-cause mortality and cancer (62). Other consequences of hypovitaminosis D can be headaches and muscle pains (63).

Moreover, there is evidence supporting the role of vitamin D (plasma levels above 30 ng/mL) in the protection against arterial hypertension and a possible association with glucose metabolism (15).

The Point of View of Chronic Fatigue Syndrome

Chronic fatigue syndrome, better known as myalgic encephalopathy, is defined as a condition with an incompletely clear etiology characterized by debilitating tiredness lasting more than six months, associated with at least four other symptoms: non-restorative sleep, impaired memory and/or concentration, episodes of headaches, post-exertional malaise, muscle pain and polyarthralgia, and sore throat. The most accredited pathogenetic hypothesis is linked to phenomena triggered by viral diseases and conditions such as hypocortisolism, but in reality, this condition must be classified as a complex pathology with repercussions in the multifactorial cognitive behavioral field. At the moment, to our knowledge, no drug therapy has proven effective, so the therapy is based on cognitive behavioral therapy and graded physical therapy. A work by Earl et al. (2017) investigated the relationship between this syndrome and plasmatic vitamin D values without identifying hypovitaminosis condition in these patients. This evidence appears in contrast with what was reported in previous studies such as that of Berkovitz et al., which, on the contrary, demonstrated low plasma levels of vitamin D in these patients; in fact, one of the conclusions of this study concerned the hypothesis of recommending vitamin D supplementation in these patients and sun exposure, as well as the use of foods rich in vitamin D. A more recent, large study investigated the relationship between chronic fatigue or low energy levels and low circulating levels of 25OHD; the data emerging from this study suggest that a clinically relevant protective effect of vitamin D on fatigue is unlikely, so these authors believe that the correction of hypovitaminosis D is unlikely to be protective against fatigue.

Conclusions

The present work aims at reviewing the state of the art on vitamin D effects on the mitigation of fatigue state. Important findings about the impact of vitamin D in specific fatigue-related molecular pathways, such as inflammation and oxidative stress, emerge from the literature.

Despite the promising potential effects of vitamin D on these pathways can be hypothesized, limited data on in vivo studies (especially in human cohorts) are currently present in the literature. In addition, where studies in human cohorts are available, conflicting findings emerge. Also, despite the fact that vitamin D deficiency is recurrent in patients affected by several different diseases, scarce data on the impact of supplementation on fatigue as an outcome have been collected until now. These limitations of the current knowledge on the potential impact of vitamin D on fatigue significantly constrain the translatability of research findings into clinical practice. Concerning the level of evidence in different pathophysiological conditions, results can be summarized as follows. A clear connection between fatigue and vitamin D in elderly people emerged. Also, a good response against fatigue in multiple sclerosis patients when supplemented with vitamin D has been documented. In contrast, very little and mostly conflicting evidence has been published so far regarding the other pathologies considered in this review (i.e., fibromyalgia, rheumatological diseases, myasthenia gravis, and

cancer). Thus, according to the current level of evidence, it is not possible to support the usage of vitamin D supplementation on fatigue in these patients.

Since vitamin D supplementation might represent an easily accessible remedy to a serious condition, such as fatigue, which is also common to many severe pathologies, further studies on this topic should be conducted. In particular, given the limitations and biases of current studies as delineated throughout the manuscript, studies able to demonstrate a causal impact of vitamin D supplementation on fatigue mitigation (such as randomized controlled clinical trials) should be conducted in order to translate the evidence about vitamin D ability to control fatigue in clinical practice.

In conclusion, vitamin D supplementation appears as a promising tool that might help to mitigate the fatigue state, even if further scientific knowledge is needed to have a clear view on this topic.

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